

Relation Between Parameter of *Cirrhinus mrigala* and *Labeo rohita* from Bago Market, Bago Township

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Abstract

This study recorded the length-weight relationship of conditional factor for commercially fish species of Order Cypriniformes namely *Cirrhinus mrigala* and *Labeo rohita* from Bago market, Bago Township. A total number of each 120 specimens of fish species were collected for analysis. Length-weight relationship was calculated for these fish species and found significant. The correlation coefficient (r) was significant and observed to be 0.931 in *C. mrigala* and 0.943 in *L. rohita*. The regression coefficient (b) value of *C. mrigala* was 3.69 in positive allometric and *L. rohita* was closed to 3(2.99) in nearly isometric. The mean condition factors of *C. mrigala* and *L. rohita* could be regarded as good feeding condition and found to be quite satisfactory in the study area.

keywords: length weight relationship, environmental condition, growth.

Introduction

Fish and fish products are crucial important in the nutrition and livelihoods of the Myanmar people. Fish is second only to rice in the Myanmar diet (FAO, 2003).

About 90% of all fresh water fisheries occur in developing countries. Fishes are valuable sources of high- grade protein and other organic products. The muscular tissues of flesh of a fish are made up of as to 80% water, about 16% to 23% proteins, and a greater or lesser amount (Norman, 1977).

The mathematical relationship between length and weight of fishes is a practical index suitable for understanding their survival, growth, maturity, reproduction and general well being. It was initially used to obtain information on the growth condition of fish and to find out whether the somatic growth was isometric or allometric. Fishes are said to exhibit isometric growth when length increases in equal proportions with body weight for constant specific gravity (Reynold, 1968).

Conditional factor studies take into consideration the health and general well being of a fish as related to its environment. *Cirrhinus mrigala* is used as aquaculture species. This species command a good market price and consumer demand. The fish flesh is an excellent source of protein, has very little fat, carries a good amount of minerals and vitamins A and D. *Labeo rohita* is the most generally esteemed for eating purposes. It is also a much domesticated freshwater fish because of its excellence as food. *L. rohita* is a highly preferred carp and fetches comparatively high market price. They are either market fresh in the local market or carried to nearby urban markets with ice (Wikipedia, 2017).

The objective of this study is to study the morphological characters of studied species, to record length and weight sizes of collected fish species and to assess length-weight relationships and conditional factors of studied species.

Material and Methods

Study area and study site

Collections of studied fish species were undertaken from Bago Market, Bago Township. Local fishermen captured various species of fishes including the studied two species from Bago River, Bago Region. It is about 16° 45' North Latitude and 96° 15' East Longitude, the Bago River joins Yangon river and then empties into the Gulf of Mottama. The study period lasted from December 2016 to February 2018.

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Collection of fish specimens

A total number of each 20 specimens of *Cirrhinus mrigala* and *Labeo rohita* were randomly collected monthly to evaluate the length-weight relationship, condition factors. During the study period, the collected specimens were photographed in fresh condition to obtain for their natural size, weight and colour. Sample random sampling technique used followed after Cochran (2007).

Data analysis

Length-weight relationships were calculated to determine the condition and growth patterns of fish (Bagenal and Tesch, 1978). The length-weight relationship was calculated by the exponential equation for combined sexes.

$$W = aL^b \text{ (Le Cren, 1951)}$$

W = the weight (g) of fish in grams

L = the total length of fish in centimeters

a = the intercept of the regression line on the Y axis

b = the slope of the regression line

Condition factor studies take into consideration as related to its environment (Reynold, 1968). The condition factor (K) was calculated according to Pauly (1983).

$$K \% = W/L^3 \times 100$$

Where K = Condition factor; W = Weight in gram; L = Length in cm

Identification

Identifications of fish were made after Talwar and Jhingran (1991) and Rainboth (1996).

Bago River

Map of the study site (Source: Internet)

Bago Market

Results

Systematic position of Studied species

The systematic position of recorded fish species was based on Talwar and Jhingran (1991) and Rainboth (1996).

Kingdom	- Animalia
Phylum	- Chordata
Class	- Osteichthyes
Order	- Osteoglossiformes
Family	- Cyprinidae
Genus	- <i>Cirrhinus</i>
Species	- <i>C. mrigala</i> (Hamilton- Buchanan, 1822)
Common name	- Mrigal
Local name	- Nga-gyin
Genus	- <i>Labeo</i>
Species	- <i>L. rohita</i> (Hamilton-Buchanan, 1822)
Common name	- Rohu
Local name	- Nga-myit-chin

Cirrhinus mrigala

Labeo rohita

Table.1 Monthly variation in length, weight and mean condition factor for *Cirrhinus mrigala*

Months	Sample size (n)	Body Length (cm)		Body weight (g)		Mean condition factor (K)
		Mean±SD	Range	Mean±SD	Range	
December	20	36.33±1.97	34.2-40.6	1031.75±133.91	927-1343	2.15±0.12
January	20	40.85±1.83	38.0-43.4	1374.05±160.27	1604-1120	2.01±0.06
February	20	45.53±0.73	44.6-46.5	2413.55±129.18	2248-2591	2.55±0.02
March	20	41.30±2.51	37.6-46.2	1682.05±395.04	1157-2517	2.40±0.56
April	20	47.12±1.64	42.5-49.9	2815.20±203.83	2495-2979	2.70±0.20
May	20	46.62±2.35	43.3-50.7	2636.10±664.03	1585-3609	2.55±0.31
Total	120					

Figure 1. Monthly variation of mean length, weight and condition factor of *C. mrigala*

Figure 2. Length-weight relationship of *C. mrigala* during study period

Length-weight relationship and condition factor of *Cirrhinus mrigala*

The length-weight relationship of *Cirrhinus mrigala* was examined based on 120 specimens. The mean total length for *Cirrhinus mrigala* (n = 120) was calculated 42.96 ± 4.29 cm and the mean body weight calculated as 1992.12 ± 748.57 g. The specimens were found to range from 34.2 cm from 50.7 cm and weight was ranged between 927 g to 3609 g during the study period. According to monthly variation, the mean total length and mean body weight were 36.33 ± 1.97 cm and 1031.75 ± 133.91 g recorded as minimum in December, 2016 and the mean total length 47.12 ± 1.64 cm and the mean body weight 2815.20 ± 203.83 g was maximum in April, 2017. The length-weight relationship of *Cirrhinus mrigala* of the form $W = aL^b$ was as follow:

$$W = 0.001L^{3.685}, R^2 = 0.893, r = 0.931, p < 0.01$$

The monthly mean value of condition factor (K) was determined by the numbers of fish studied per month. The minimum K value was 2.01 ± 0.06 in January, 2017 and maximum mean value was 2.70 ± 0.20 in April, 2017. Based on overall result, the mean value of K was 2.39 ± 0.36 and the coefficient 'b' for length-weight relationship was 3.685 during the study period.

Table 2. Monthly variation in length, weight and mean condition factor for *Labeo rohita*

Months	Sample size (n)	Body Length (cm)		Body weight (g)		Mean condition factor (K)
		Mean±SD	Range	Mean±SD	Range	
December	20	33.74±1.51	30.4-35.9	1268.15±250.90	885-1904	3.29±0.57
January	20	36.33±1.22	38.1-34.3	1547.90±141.16	1210-1745	3.22±0.14
February	20	39.50±0.74	38.4-40.6	2011.55±149.14	1787-2203	3.24±0.07
March	20	38.29±2.75	33.7-42.8	1821.15±360.41	1230-2430	3.21±0.11
April	20	42.36±2.64	37.6-45.9	2525.45±468.32	1685-3097	3.28±0.11
May	20	41.25±2.49	37.8-45.9	2294.05±418.20	1761-3093	3.24±0.08
Total	120					

Figure 3. Monthly variation of mean length, weight and condition factor of *L. rohita*

Figure 4. Length-weight relationship of *L. rohita* during study period

Length-weight relationship and condition factor of *Labeo rohita*

The length-weight relationship of *Labeo rohita* was examined based on 120 specimens. The mean total length for *Labeo rohita* ($n = 120$) was calculated 38.58 ± 3.47 cm and the mean body weight calculated as 1911.36 ± 525.69 g. The specimens were found to range from 30.4 cm from 45.9 cm and weight was ranged between 885 g to 3093 g during the study period. According to monthly variation, the mean total length and mean body weight were 33.74 ± 1.51 cm and 1268.15 ± 250.90 g recorded as minimum in December, 2016 and the mean total length 42.36 ± 2.64 cm and the mean body weight 2525.45 ± 468.32 g was maximum in April, 2017. The length-weight relationship of *Labeo rohita* of the form $W = aL^b$ was as follow:

$$W = 0.035L^{2.979}, R^2 = 0.943, r = 0.973, p < 0.01$$

The monthly mean value of condition factor (K) was determined by the numbers of fish studied per month. The minimum K value was 3.21 ± 0.11 in March, 2017 and maximum mean value was 3.29 ± 0.57 in December, 2016. Based on overall result, the mean value of K was 3.25 ± 0.25 and the coefficient 'b' for length-weight relationship was 2.979 during the study period.

Discussion

The present investigation revealed that the growth performance of collected fishes were found high since the correlation coefficient 'r' exhibited high degree of correlation between the length-weight relationship although the growth being positive allometric in *Cirrhinus mrigala* and nearly isometric in *L. rohita*. Deka and Bura Gohin (2015) observed the higher proficiencies in feeding, availability of food and other associated factors for positive allometric growth in different fishes. The values of exponent 'b' were observed more than 3.38 in *L. rohita*, 3.36 in *C. mrigala* in Maji Bajaj Sangar, India (Ujjania *et al.*, 2012).

In the present study, the exponent 'b' values of *C. mrigala* and *L. rohita* were 3.69 and closed to 3 (2.99). Allen (1938) reported that such as ideal fish with a 'b' value 3 is very difficult to observe in the natural environment. The change in 'b' value mostly reflects the change in the body form when the weight of the fish gets affected by environmental factors like temperature, food supply, spawning conditions and other factors like sex, age, fishing time and area and fishing vessels (Bagenal and Tesch, 1978).

The present study showed that the mean values of condition factor (K) were all closed to one and *C. mrigala* and *L. rohita* could be regarded as good in growth and feeding condition. According to Le Cren (1951), it could be considered that the well-being state of the studied species is good in the study area. The fluctuation in the monthly K values may depend on several factors such as feeding, environmental condition, maturity and spawning in natural habitat.

Conclusion

The present study provided baseline information on length-weight relationship and conditional factor for the fishes of conservational importance. It will be useful for researchers and fishery management.

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